

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D.3.3

Boiler Performance using FPBO for a SmartCHP system

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D3.3 - Operating conditions and requirements on a component level

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Authors	Melanie Grote, Dirk Möntmann, Jochen Leuchter, Sergej Warkentin, Sangeetha Ramaswamy
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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The *SmartCHP* system combines a FPBO fuelled engine and flue gas boiler to produce electricity and heat at a high efficiency over the whole load range. A burner-boiler system is being developed which can be operated with pure FPBO or a mixture with up to 20% ethanol and flue gas from the engine with an oxygen content between 5 – 18%.

The combustion of FPBO in flue gas has been extensively studied. A 17 kW and 100 kW burner were developed and experimentally investigated under different boundary conditions in water-cooled combustion chamber (boiler). The combustion of FPBO in flue gas and the quick start of the burner even at low flue gas temperatures down to a certain O₂-limit (15% O₂ at low flue gas temperatures) works very well.

The flame speed decreases sharply with decreasing O₂ contents. Low flame speeds make it difficult to stabilize the flame in the burner. The flue gas temperatures of up to 732 K limit the flame speed drop and will help to stabilize the flame at lower oxygen contents.

Based on the requirements of the system, a boiler concept was developed, and the appropriate components were acquired.

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1. Introduction

The aim of this project is the development of a smart and flexible, small-scale combined heat and power (CHP) unit fuelled with fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) originating from different types of lignocellulosic biomasses and/or residues. The *SmartCHP* system combines a FPBO fuelled engine and flue gas boiler to produce electricity and heat at a high efficiency over the whole load range. The approach to achieve the project objective is to integrate the engine, combustor and flue gas treatment system into a single unit and perform overall system testing and evaluation for a wide range of heat and power output ratios mimicking a real environment.

The technical concept of the *SmartCHP* is outlined in Figure 1.1. The three important components of the system that will be developed in this project are the engine, the boiler and the flue gas treatment system. A burner combusts the FPBO and is integrated in the boiler. The boiler recovers heat from the flue gas. This deliverable report focusses on the burner and boiler part of the system.

Figure 1.1: Scheme of the SmartCHP-System

In Table 1.1 the properties of the flue gas after the engine for use in the burner-boiler system are summarized, defined in D3.1 - Operating conditions and requirements on a component level. Another important issue is the limitation of flue gas temperature after the boiler at the entrance to the flue gas treatment system. In the burner, FPBO with an output of 0 - 100 kW is also to be converted. It is clear that there are limitations, with regard to the oxygen concentrations and the fuel power range. Nevertheless, the aim of the development is to realize the widest possible operating range. For a proper functionality of the gas cleaning catalyst the flue gas temperature after the boiler should stay in a range between 270 - 480 °C.

Table 1.1: Properties of the flue gas from the engine for use in the burner

Flue gas	Minimum	Maximum	Unit
Oxygen - O ₂	4	18	v %
Carbon dioxide - CO ₂	2	16	v %
Flow rate	140	250	Nm ³ /hr
Temperature	175	550	°C

Based on these specifications, a burner-boiler system is being developed which can be operated with pure FPBO or a mixture with up to 20% ethanol.

2. Burner and boiler development

Different burner systems and atomizer were composed and rated in terms of their suitability for burning FPBO with a flue gas from a lean-burn engine. A number of preliminary tests with different burners were carried out. It was found that the procured yellow flame burner from Kroll with external mixing two-substance nozzle was not suitable for the planned application. The same applies to the blue burner.

The swirl pressure nozzle, which was initially rated lower, performed well in the hardware in the loop test over a longer period in combination with the Nuert pump since the orifices of the nozzle for 100 kW FPBO are large enough to prevent blocking. The following diagram shows the result of a hardware-in-the-loop test with nozzle from Schlick (0.8 mm, 70°), standard oil preheater and fuel pump (Nuert). The FPBO was changed after 50.5 and 120 h since the operation temperature of 50° C causes ageing of the fuel. The mass flow of the fuel stays at a high level for about 190 h. However, the standard oil preheater was blocked during combustion tests and had to be replaced by a more robust device.

In summary, it was determined, as also shown by the tests, that a swirl burner with a pressure swirl nozzle is best suitable for the planned application.

In order to estimate the stability of the combustion process, the laminar flame speeds were calculated for the substitute Diesel and the flue gas mixtures of the Diesel engine, see Table 2.1. The calculations were performed with Cantera. Decane was used as surrogate fuel and the mechanism of Ranzi [2].

The flame speed decreases sharply with decreasing O₂ contents. Low flame speeds make it difficult to stabilize the flame in the burner. The exhaust gas temperatures of up to 732 K limit the flame speed drop and will help to stabilize the flame at low oxygen content. Presumably, the flame will no longer be stable at an oxygen content of 7.2 % in the exhaust gas. Low heat losses of combustion zone maybe enhance stability at this point. When designing the burner, it must be taken into account that the incoming flue gas volume flows are influenced by the oxygen amount and temperature of engine flue gas.

Table 2.1: Operation points Diesel engine flue gas (BTG, average), flame speed of Diesel with flue gas at $\lambda = 1.1$ and volume flow increase of flue gas compared to reference point: 21% O₂, $T = 293$ K, $\lambda = 1.1$, $p = 1$ atm

O ₂ content	Temperature	Flame speed	Volume flow increase*
17.7 %	405 K	34.04 cm/s	68 %
15.8 %	456 K	28.28 cm/s	89 %
11.6 %	570 K	14.82 cm/s	136 %
7.2 %	732 K	6.30 cm/s	203 %

No values are yet available for operation of the engine with FPBO. Qualitatively, however, similar values and correlations will result.

A CFD-study with the burner described in the following section was carried out to aid the design of the burner. Important findings from this are:

- The optimum igniter position can be determined using CFD calculations. When comparing the test and simulation, the following results were obtained:
 - A good flammability in case of sufficient liquid and gaseous fuel concentration around igniter was detected.
 - One igniter cannot cover the entire range with regard to fuel performance and exhaust gas mixtures.
- Furthermore, the flame front moves upstream and becomes more stable by
 - increasing the oxygen content of oxidizer
 - decreasing the cooling of combustion zone
 - decreasing the flame tube diameter
 - increasing the air nozzle diameter

A boiler concept was developed based on the experimental experience and investigations in the project Residue2Heat [1]. The 100 kW FPBO burner will be operated in a standard non-condensing oil-boiler. After the boiler, the flue gas is cleaned by a flue gas cleaning unit, see Figure 2.1. Since purification stage requires temperatures between 270 - 480°C, the heat exchanger surfaces of the boiler should be reduced to achieve the target.

Figure 2.1: Boiler concept

One result of the project Residue2Heat was that the FPBO flame needs more space compared to a domestic heating-oil flame. Therefore, a boiler for twice the burner capacity is procured.

3. Preliminary studies on a small burner

Burner tests were initially carried out with domestic heating oil as a substitute for FPBO. With different burner configurations and compositions of the conducted engine flue gas, the flame behavior was investigated. The engine flue gas was provided in two different ways for this purpose. First, the non-combustible components were replaced by nitrogen and a mixture of air and nitrogen was fed to the burner. Then the burner exhaust gas was produced with the help of a heating oil boiler, to which air was added. Figure 3.1 shows the burner with flame tube, air and oil nozzle. Figure 3.2 shows the second test method where actual flue gas is used for the burner tests. The generated flue gas (right side Figure 3.2) flows through the metal hose to the burner (left side of Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.1: Burner for tests

Figure 3.2: Test rig for burner tests

3.1 Domestic heating oil with artificial flue gas

The burner settings were optimized (air nozzle $d = 24$ mm, blade angle = 10°) and the stable operating points are shown in Figure 3.3, where the flame is not extinguished, and a CO value is below 500 ppm. Three different fuel inputs between 14.2 – 16.69 kW were examined at an air ratio of about 1.1. Air and nitrogen were fed into the burner at a temperature of 20° C. The values in the box indicate the oxygen content of the simulated engine flue gas (before combustion). The minimum value was 12.8 % oxygen.

Figure 3.3: Stable operation points of burner test with best burner configuration and air-nitrogen flue gas, domestic heating oil

3.2 Domestic heating oil with real flue gas

Using the same burner geometry and a modified version with 28 mm air nozzle diameter, tests were carried out with flue gas from the heating oil boiler (right side Figure 3.2). The temperature of flue gas mixture entering the boiler was 20 – 100°C. An air ratio of 1.1 was set. In Figure 3.4, the pressure upstream of the burner is plotted against the oxygen content in the supplied flue gas mixture. Stable operation points for both burner configurations and different fuel inputs 10 – 13.6 kW are marked in. Lowest oxygen contents between 13 – 16 % were achieved for the burner with 28 mm air nozzle. Compared to the studies with nitrogen admixtures, the limit value with respect to the oxygen content in the feed is 2% higher. The best performance was observed at fuel input of 11.6 kW (oil pressure 10 bar). The perfect position of the igniter (17 mm downstream) ensures a proper start over the entire range of oxygen contents 21 – 14.2%.

Figure 3.4: Stable operation points of burner test, air nozzle diameter 24 mm and 28 mm, blade angle = 10°, flue gas supply from heating oil boiler, domestic heating oil used as fuel.

3.3 FPBO with artificial flue gas

After the system tests with domestic heating oil, the burner was converted for use with FPBO. The oil pump was replaced by a Nuert pump. A series of tests were carried out using artificial flue gas. Deposits on the flame tube and clogging of the oil preheater and nozzle were found, which made modification of the burner necessary. A larger nozzle was used (0.85 gph 60°HR). The flame tube was insulated and the air-nitrogen mixture was preheated to about 175°C. This is the lowest estimated flue gas temperature from engine entering the burner, see Table 1.1. The preheater was replaced by a heated tube with an inner diameter of 8 mm. The fuel, FPBO with 20% ethanol, was heated to 60°C. The air nozzle was modified in several stages.

The stable operations points for the best modification are shown in Figure 3.5. Compared to the tests with domestic heating oil, in this case the total volume flow of the oxidizer was fixed and the nitrogen content was continuously increased. As a result, not only the O₂ content but also the air ratio decreases. The lowest obtained O₂ content is 14.5%. The operating range can be extended by increasing the preheating temperature. This was being investigated with the 100 kW burner, see chapter 5.

Figure 3.5: Stable operation points of burner test with 80% FPBO and 20% ethanol, air nozzle diameter 25 mm, pipe insert, 12 x 2.5 mm holes, blade angle = 20°, preheated air-nitrogen mixture 170°C

3.4 FPBO ignition with artificial flue gas

In parallel, the starting capability was investigated for all modifications when a cold gas mixture of the burner was supplied. Figure 3.6 shows the stable ignition points for a non-preheated air-nitrogen mixture.

The ignition is much more stable with low volume flow. It therefore seems sensible to pass only a partial flow of the exhaust gas through the burner for starting. A minimum oxygen content of 15.8% was achieved. If necessary, the range can be extended by further reducing the volume flow and electrically preheating the exhaust gas stream. This will be further investigated on the 100 kW burner.

Figure 3.6: Stable ignition points of burner test with 17 kW, fuel input, 80% FPBO and 20% ethanol, air nozzle diameter 25 mm, pipe insert, 12 x 2.5 mm holes, blade angle = 20°, non-preheated air-nitrogen mixture

4. Burner and boiler design

The best burner concept was scaled for a fuel input of 100 kW. Swirl number and flue gas velocity was kept constant. The burner was constructed and delivered by MEKU. Figure 4.1 and 4.2 show the burner and the CAD drawing. The oil nozzle is protected from the high temperatures of the exhaust gas with a pipe insert and small air nozzle. The swirl generator is located directly in front of the air nozzle. The nozzle and the inner protective cover can be moved axially. The air nozzle can be modified and changed if necessary.

Figure 4.1: Burner 100 kW for FPBO constructed by MEKU, side view with flue gas inlet (left), front view with air nozzle and ignition electrodes (right)

Figure 4.2: CAD drawing burner 100 kW for FPBO constructed by MEKU

CFD calculations were used to verify functionality and swirl number of about 0.8 - 1 (Figure 4.3). It has been ensured that no fuel reaches the wall of the flame tube or returns to the nozzle.

Figure 4.3: CFD simulation of the 100 kW burner, FBPO 80% and 20% ethanol, non-preheated air, lambda 1.5, insulation of flame tube, temperatures (left), velocities (right)

According to the design criteria from Chapter 2, a boiler was selected and purchased. The boiler Logano plus GE515 (195 kW) is a low temperature boiler which can be operated without separate condenser. The exhaust gas in the boiler flows radially into the water-cooled heat exchanger via several elongated openings. These are partially closed to ensure the necessary exhaust gas temperature.

Figure 4.4: Boiler Logano plus GE515 (195 kW) without condenser form Bosch Buderus GmbH, boiler with insulation and covering (left), principle sketch openings to the heat exchanger (right), Source: Bosch Buderus GmbH

5. Burner and boiler tests

The boiler was installed in the laboratories of OWI and the MEKU-burner was integrated (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1: Test bench 100 kW at OWI with non-insulated boiler and burner from MEKU (left), view into the boiler (right)

In order to get closer to the real burner exhaust gas, it is possible to add CO₂ to the air in addition to nitrogen in the current test setup and thus produce almost real exhaust gas mixtures. CO₂ has a much higher heat capacity and significantly reduces the flame temperature compared to nitrogen. A preheater can be used to heat the artificial flue gas mixture to the desired temperature, see Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Process diagram of test bench

The tests are performed with a fuel mixture of 80% FPBO and 20% ethanol. The fuel can be heated with the help of an oil preheater or a heater around the oil tank. Burner emissions at different preheat temperatures and O₂ limits are shown in Figure 1. A simulated exhaust gas mixture with nitrogen and air was produced for the tests. The pyrolysis oil was preheated to approx. 40°C. Fuel input was set to 70 – 100 kW. The air ratio was 1.1 – 1.2. At each setting, the burner could also be ignited. The increased temperatures of the supplied flue gas facilitate the start of the burner. No burner fuel deposits have formed in the burner and boiler during experiments.

Figure 5.3: Burner emissions, fuel input 70 - 80 kW

Figure 5.4: Burner limits, fuel input 100 kW

The emissions are coherent. The minimum O₂ levels of the supplied flue gas with a stable flame decrease with temperature. However, the course is not linear and should be investigated in detail further on. Experiments are to be carried out with different fuel inputs, air ratios and a flue gas mixture consisting of nitrogen and CO₂. In addition, geometric modifications to the burner will be used to increase emissions and the operating range.

6. Conclusion

The combustion of diesel and fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) in flue gas has been extensively studied. A 17 kW and 100 kW burner were developed and experimentally investigated under different boundary conditions in water-cooled combustion chamber (boiler). The combustion of FPBO in exhaust gas and the quick start of the burner even at low exhaust gas temperatures down to a certain O₂-limit (15% O₂ at low flue gas temperatures) works very well.

Based on the requirements of the system, a boiler concept was developed and the appropriate components were acquired. Further investigations with the burner-boiler system also at higher flue gas temperatures are planned.

7. References

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